

APPLICATION OF THE ADOPTED ECONOMIC TERMS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: in this article information about the emergence of new terms, the sources of the formation of new economic terms, the scope of their general use, the shortcomings of this system and ways to eliminate them is provided.

Key words: term, terminology, neologism, word acquisition, ownership, product exchange.

In the context of the innovative development of economic sectors on a global scale and their direct impact on the internal economic reforms of any country in the conditions of the current acceleration of globalization and integration processes, entrepreneurs, businessmen, specialists in the field of economics working in the country are required to have excellent knowledge of foreign languages, English and Russian.

Currently, entrepreneurs working in the fields of economy, as well as all the professional personnel who are developing in the field, have the opportunity to communicate freely in world languages, including English and Russian, which makes it possible to introduce innovations created in developed countries in the course of their activities. It opens the door to a wide range of opportunities to become familiar with the achievements and existing problems in the fields. This is one step with world development.

From the beginning of the 19th century, the Uzbek language gradually gave way to the Russian language. All documents are kept in Russian, and the new terms that are in circulation are adopted. This situation gradually weakened the Uzbek scientific language, and subsequently led to the complete withdrawal of Uzbek terms from many areas of the economy. Today, along with many other sciences, there is a need to enrich Uzbek language terms in economics as well.

Therefore, along with all world languages, it is necessary to revive Uzbek terms and terms, to solve the above and other similar problems. At the same time, the leading directions of the economy: accounting-finance, econometrics, management, marketing, logistics and international economic relations are convenient and the difference from the previous explanatory dictionaries is : In order to bring the terms existing in the old Uzbek language into circulation, and to revive the terms from the works of the founders of the Uzbek language, Alisher Navoi, Mahmud

Kashgari, etc. there is a need to develop an explanatory dictionary that will serve the development of science and occupy a special place on the shelf of every economist.

In the period of current socio-economic and scientific-technical fundamental changes, unique concepts are emerging. That is, during the high-level scientific and technical revolution, new subjects and concepts began to appear in all fields of production, science and technology. In particular, new terms are appearing in Uzbek economic dictionaries. It should be noted that this terminological system has not been able to find its full expression due to the lack of attention paid to economic terms coming from English and Russian languages.

In the present conditions, a new way of thinking is being used in all aspects of social life. In particular, such an approach has fully covered social sciences, because its consequences are related to human life in society, future development, and the world surrounding it. That is why social relations are promoted in the first place in the relations between people, nations and states. The situation in this field has completely changed in our republic. Foreign economic relations have further developed. A wide path to economic relations with many countries of the world has been opened. These factors caused new economic terms to appear in the Uzbek language. Therefore, at the current stage of the development of science and technology, it is important to study economic terms from an economic point of view. In particular, there is a need to study a number of issues, such as the sources of the formation of new economic terms, the scope of their general use, the shortcomings of this system and the ways to eliminate them. In addition, it includes the collection and systematization of economic terms used in the current Uzbek language. In fact, although they serve to fully express the content of new economic terms, which have been increasing in quantity in recent years, it is rather inconvenient to use them in practice and remember them. It should be noted that almost all scientists who have dealt with the issue of terms have tried to give their definition. Because every industry has a term that is used within that industry, to be more precise, people who have a certain profession or specialty often use the specific terms of this or that industry. This forms the speech of the owner of the profession and creates conditions for the culture of mutual speech and communication. For example, in the written or oral speech of economists, it is natural to use terms that are used only in a narrow circle, such as product exchange (commodity turnover), small ownership, allocation of funds, rent. It is self-evident that such terms are not used in the speech of a professional far away from economics. At the same time, there are a number of economic terms that are used equally in the speech of almost all speakers of a particular language. For example, market, goods, trade, money, buyer, marketer, seller, etc. are among them.

It should also be said that there is a huge difference between economic terms that have been traditionally preserved in the language since ancient times and modern economic terms. While the quantity of old economic terms is quite limited, the terms related to the field of economy are incomparably richer due to the increasing need for economic terms in the current new era, that is, in the conditions of the market economy.

Terms related to the economy, recognizing the humanity of man, first encountered the concept of "economy". To put it more precisely, everyone who thought about the future of life first of all thought about finding something and taking care of it, how to use it, saving and searching, and acted on this basis. In fact, it is known to everyone that the basis of the economy is the solution of this issue. Let's take such a simple fact. First of all, instead of thinking about the well-being of his life, a person works tirelessly, worries about the future, the appearance of his children, raising them and making them comfortable, and finally, his connects labor results with the market, etc. It was at this time that concepts such as "economy" and "economy" began to form in people's minds, and all these were the first buds of "economy", which has become a science today.

Gradually, as the society began to develop, new laws were discovered in the economy, as in other areas. The way to start studying the economy was opened, in the end, the real economy, which formed the basis of our life in the present period, was realized.

Such factors led to the decision of the specific terminological system of the economy. So, the economic terminology has gone through several stages until it reached its current state. Economic terminology has gone through three qualitatively different historical stages. They consist of:

1. The period of economic terminology until the beginning of the 20th century.
2. Development of economic terminology in the 20s-90s of the 20th century.
3. Development of economic terminology in the post-independence period.

It should be noted that the formation of economic terms dates back to the distant past. To be sure of this, it is necessary to turn to historical written monuments. From this point of view, the work of Mahmud Kashgari, the founder of Turkic lexicography, "Devonu Lugotit Turk", several dictionaries created before the revolution, representatives of Uzbek literature, in particular Alisher Navoi, M. Babur and others, artistic, scientific, artistic works are considered to be sources that have a special place in the development of Uzbek economic terms. Another important source that records a number of economic terms that are still widely used in the Uzbek language is Yusuf Khos Khojib, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Muqimi, Furqat, Ogahi, and hundreds of economic terms used in their original and figurative meanings. The studied sources show that the

Uzbek language reached a specific system state during the formation and development stage of economic terminology up to the beginning of the 20th century, but, although there is no clearly organized terminology, it has been used in oral speech or in written sources. The fact that some of these terms are still used today is a product of the long and complex development of spoken and written language through economic and cultural relations between Tajiks, Arabs, Persians, Uzbeks and other Turkic peoples.

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